

Buffer Access Monitoring for Enhanced Buffer Overflow Detection in Fuzzing

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Abstract—Buffer overflows remain one of the most critical and widespread vulnerabilities in software systems. Traditional fuzzing techniques often lack the precision required to reliably detect buffer overflows. This paper presents BUFFERMONITOR, a novel approach to enhancing buffer overflow detection by integrating a comprehensive buffer monitoring system into fuzzing frameworks. Using the LLVM compiler framework, we instrument the system under test to collect detailed memory access information, including the distance of each access from buffer boundaries. By prioritizing inputs that generate minimal distances to these boundaries, our method significantly improves the likelihood of detecting potential overflows. This approach not only increases the possibility of identifying buffer overflows but can also identify them with greater accuracy than AddressSanitizer. This provides a robust solution for enhancing software security.

Keywords—Buffer Access Monitoring; Buffer overflows; Fuzzing; Security Testing; Memory access information

1. INTRODUCTION

Buffer overflows belong to the most critical vulnerabilities, according to CWE Top Ten 2023 [1] and CWE Top 25 Most Dangerous Software Weaknesses 2023 [2], and can pose significant risks when exploited by attackers. These vulnerabilities are most commonly found in C/C++ programs, as these languages enable programmers to directly manage memory without implementing checks to ensure that boundaries are not exceeded during memory access. During runtime buffer overflows will remain undetected because of the runtime environment’s inability to identify such overflows [3]. This makes buffer overflow detection and repair quite challenging. Therefore, it is crucial to have effective tools to detect memory access violations, such as buffer overflows and buffer overreads¹.

Sanitizers such as AddressSanitizer (ASan) are commonly used to observe buffer overflows. Nevertheless, buffer overflows can only be observed if the memory access is violated at runtime. This requires the use of corresponding input data capable of triggering the vulnerability.

Fuzzing is a technique that has been developed to address this challenge. It involves the systematic generation of test data, which is then used to identify and trigger vulnerabilities in software programs. By automating the test data generation process, a fuzzer increases the likelihood of uncovering vulnerabilities that might otherwise go undetected.

The effectiveness of a fuzzer largely depends on its ability to generate promising inputs². Numerous strategies have been developed to enhance the efficiency of fuzzing tools. In particular, evolutionary fuzzing, often implemented in coverage-guided fuzzers, has proven to be highly effective in identifying vulnerabilities [4]. Evolutionary fuzzing focuses on continuously evolving and refining inputs to explore new behavior of the System Under Test (SUT). However, traditional fuzzing approaches often struggle to effectively consider and analyze memory accesses, which are crucial for identifying security vulnerabilities such as buffer overflows. Effective detection and mitigation of buffer overflow vulnerabilities require precise monitoring of buffer accesses during runtime. To address this limitation, we propose the integration of buffer access monitoring with the fuzzing process.

For this purpose, we introduce BUFFERMONITOR, a comprehensive buffer access monitoring instrumentation module designed to enhance the detection of buffer overflow vulnerabilities. BUFFERMONITOR uses the Low Level Virtual Machine (LLVM) compiler framework to instrument the source code of the SUT to monitor buffer accesses and determine how close an access is to the buffer’s boundary. This information is crucial for identifying potential memory access instructions in the code that could lead to buffer overflows. Furthermore, BUFFERMONITOR can identify buffer overflows more precisely than other sanitizers (e.g. ASan).

BUFFERMONITOR offers the potential to combine the exhaustive code coverage of fuzzing with the precision of buffer access monitoring. By integrating BUFFERMONITOR with evolutionary fuzzing, our approach enhances the effectiveness of fuzzing campaigns in uncovering buffer overflow vulnerabilities.

As a prototype, we integrated the BUFFERMONITOR into the American Fuzzy Lop (AFL) and conducted an initial evaluation. The remaining sections of this paper are organized as follows: Section 2 discusses related work; Section 3 presents the instrumentation module for the buffer access monitoring; and Section 4 describes the integration into the fuzzing workflow. Section 5 addresses the evaluation results, and Section 6 concludes the paper.

2. RELATED WORK

Fuzzing tools have been widely used to identify software vulnerabilities. Tools like AFL [5] and LibFuzzer [6] use var-

¹In the following, we use buffer overflow as a generic term for both

²The definition of ‘promising’ inputs varies depending on the specific fuzzer and the fuzzing target. Different fuzzers may prioritize different types of inputs based on their intended goals and the nature of the software being tested.

ious strategies, such as mutation-based and generation-based fuzzing, to generate test cases. These tools use a coverage-guided approach to maximize code coverage and uncover new program paths. While they are effective at identifying a wide range of vulnerabilities, they cannot precisely monitor memory accesses, which limits their effectiveness in detecting buffer overflows.

Various approaches have been developed to identify buffer overflows. One of the most widely used tools is ASan [7], which instruments the SUT to detect memory errors such as buffer overflows. ASan operates by maintaining a shadow memory to track the status of each byte in the allocated memory regions. Although ASan is effective, it can only detect overflows that occur during runtime and accesses shadow memory. Furthermore, ASan relies on the appropriate inputs to trigger the vulnerabilities. Consequently, it did not recognize buffer overflows that exceeded the shadow memory threshold and did not guide the exploration toward potential buffer overflows.

Static analysis tools like Splint [8], ARCHER [9], or BOON [10] aim to identify potential overflow by analyzing the source code. While these tools are able to identify buffer overflows, they can be computationally expensive and produce a high number of false positives [11]. Dynamic analysis tools like Valgrind [12] can detect memory errors, including buffer overflows, by simulating every instruction and monitoring all memory accesses. However, Valgrind incurs significant performance overhead, making it less suitable for large-scale fuzzing campaigns.

Recent advancements in hybrid fuzzing techniques aim to combine the strengths of both fuzzing and symbolic execution. Tools like Driller [13] and QSYM [14] leverage symbolic execution to guide the fuzzer toward unexplored paths and hard-to-reach code regions. These approaches have shown promise in improving code coverage and vulnerability detection. However, they still face challenges related to scalability and the overhead of symbolic execution.

MemFuzz [15] proposes using memory accesses to guide the fuzzing process. By closely monitoring how a program interacts with memory, MemFuzz aims to improve the identification of vulnerabilities that may not be easily detectable through traditional coverage-guided fuzzing techniques. This approach aligns with our methodology of integrating code instrumentation for buffer access monitoring within the fuzzing framework. In contrast, our approach involves not only monitoring buffer access but also calculating the distance of each access from the buffer’s boundaries. This allows us to prioritize inputs that are closer to the boundary, which are more likely to expose buffer overflows.

Our approach builds upon existing fuzzing tools by integrating buffer access information within the fuzzing workflow. By leveraging the LLVM compiler framework, we have implemented a mechanism for tracking memory allocations and accesses, thereby enabling precise detection of buffer overflows. In contrast to ASan and MemFuzz, our approach not only identifies buffer overflows but also prioritizes seeds

that are likely to trigger them, enhancing the efficacy of the fuzzing process.

3. BUFFERMONITOR

BUFFERMONITOR closely examines how a system interacts with its buffers by monitoring the creation of buffers and their access. In particular, BUFFERMONITOR provides useful information about potential overflow by reporting for each access the distance from the buffer’s boundary.

By instrumenting the SUT at the LLVM Intermediate Representation (LLVM IR) level, we ensure that the monitoring is both comprehensive and efficient, covering all buffer types (heap, stack, global) and access patterns.

To monitor buffer accesses, an LLVM Pass was developed to instrument the code at points where memory operations occur. LLVM Passes are an integral part of the LLVM compiler framework, which performs code transformations on programs during compilation. By inserting additional instructions, LLVM Passes can collect data about various aspects of program execution, such as memory accesses. The LLVM Pass for BUFFERMONITOR involves inserting checks before and after buffer access to log relevant information, such as the addresses being accessed and the size of the buffer.

The code snippet shown in Listing 1 is provided to illustrate the operation of BUFFERMONITOR, demonstrating how the code is instrumented to include instructions for buffer access monitoring. This example helps to clarify the steps involved in integrating the buffer monitoring system with the SUT, highlighting the points at which memory allocations and access are tracked.

3.1 Monitoring Buffer Allocation

Since passes are executed on the LLVM IR level, it is necessary to identify the instructions responsible for memory allocation. As shown in Table 1, various functions are used for memory allocation depending on the memory location.

Function	Memory Location	Description
<code>alloca</code>	Stack / Global	Allocation of stack memory segments
<code>malloc</code>	Heap	Allocation of heap memory
<code>calloc</code>	Heap	Allocation and initialization of heap memory
<code>realloc</code>	Heap	Reallocation of heap memory
<code>new</code>	Heap	Allocation of heap memory in C++

Table 1: Overview of different memory allocation functions

The `alloca` instruction is used for the allocation of stack memory segments. To detect allocations that reserve memory on the heap, the functions `malloc`, `calloc`, and `realloc` must be considered. Memory allocation via the `new` keyword, which is used in C++ programs, is also considered by the instrumentation. Heap and global allocations are handled in the same manner as allocations of stack memory.

Listing 2 shows the code snippet of the instrumented LLVM IR code that results from the first line of the example in Listing 1. This listing illustrates how the original LLVM IR

code is instrumented by BUFFERMONITOR. The instrumented instructions are highlighted.

```

1 char buffer[10];
2 for (int i = 0; i < 10; i++)
3     buffer[i] = 'A';

```

Listing 1: Code example initializing a character array of size 10 and writing to it.

```

1 %3 = alloca [10 x i8], align 1
2 %4 = bitcast [10 x i8]* %3 to i8*
3 call void @store_buffer(i32 13, i8* %4, i64
4     10, i64 0)

```

Listing 2: LLVM IR for memory allocation with highlighted BUFFERMONITOR instrumentation

For each memory allocation, the function `store_buffer` is added. The `store_buffer` function stores the relevant information of the created buffer in a hash map. The hash map includes details such as the buffer’s size, the address of the allocated memory, a unique ID, and later the buffer indices accessed. The use of a hash map allows for efficient storage and retrieval of buffer information, enabling the monitoring system to quickly access and update the data as necessary. An exemplary representation of the hash map can be found in Table 2.

ID	Buffer Size	Memory Address	Distance	Accessed
1	10 bytes	0x7ffdc123000	5	0, 1, 5
2	20 bytes	0x7ffdc124000	4	0, 5, 16

Table 2: Exemplary hash map for storing buffer information.

3.2 Monitoring Buffer Access

Detecting and gathering memory access is the main task of the buffer monitor pass. When accessing a particular memory element, the address of the element to be accessed must be determined. The address calculation is performed by the `getelementptr` instruction. It is important to note that the `getelementptr` instruction does not itself access any memory but rather calculates the memory addresses.

In case of a buffer overflow, an erroneous invocation of the `getelementptr` instruction occurs. This results in the calculation of an address that lies outside the buffer boundary. This is followed by a subsequent call to the `store` instruction, which attempts to write to the unauthorized memory, or the `load` instruction, which attempts to read from unauthorized memory.

Upon the execution of a `getelementptr` instruction, the primary concern is the index being accessed. Initially, the hash map is queried to determine the existence of the buffer being accessed, utilizing the address of the memory in question. This step is crucial since the `getelementptr` instruction can be

applied not only to memory regions that require detection by BUFFERMONITOR but also to structs.

If an entry corresponding to the buffer exists in the hash map, the index computed by the `getelementptr` instruction is recorded in the hash map. By knowing of the address, size, and indices being accessed, the distance can be calculated. The distance of a buffer indicates how far an access is from the buffer boundary (in bytes). This distance (d) is calculated from the size of the buffer (s) and the index (i) being accessed:

$$d = s - i$$

The calculation of the distance is illustrated in Figure 1. It is important to note that once the distance is less than or equal to zero, a buffer overflow is detected. This condition indicates that memory access has exceeded the buffer’s boundaries, thereby confirming an overflow. By monitoring the distances of memory accesses to buffer boundaries, the system can promptly identify overflow conditions and flag them for further analysis.

Program: A

Distance: $8 - 1 = 7$

Program: B

Distance: $8 - 6 = 2$

Figure 1: Example of buffer access and distance calculation

Given our primary focus on detecting buffer overflows, we adopt a strategy that stores the distance only if the distance is smaller than the one previously stored. In that way, we ensure to only store the memory access with the smallest distance. This selective storage mechanism ensures that we emphasize the most critical memory accesses, where the risk of an overflow is high. This methodology not only optimizes resource utilization but also maintains a high level of accuracy in identifying potential buffer overflow vulnerabilities.

Certain functions from the C Standard Library also access or manipulate memory. These functions include, but are not limited to, `memcpy`, which copies data from one memory region to another, `memset`, which fills a memory region with a specific character, `strcpy`, which copies the content of one string to another string. These functions can also lead to buffer overflows and must be handled separately. The `memcpy`

function copies n bytes from the memory area pointed to by the *src*-parameter to the memory area pointed to by *dest*-parameter. A buffer overflow occurs when the size of the destination memory *dest* is smaller than the number of bytes n to be copied from *src*. The *memcpy* function does not perform any checks to ensure the destination memory is large enough to hold the data. When a call to the *memcpy* (or similar functions, e.g. *memset* or *strcmp*) is detected, its parameters are extracted, and the largest byte manipulated by the function is calculated, which is the n -th byte in the destination or source memory.

To ensure precise monitoring of buffer accesses, two functions will be added: *update_buffer* and *store_buffer_pointer*.

- *update_buffer* is a function that updates the stored index value of a buffer when a new index is accessed where the distance to the boundary is smaller than the previously stored value. It is instrumented before every buffer access to ensure that the highest index accessed is accurately recorded.
- *store_buffer_pointer* is a function that stores the address of a buffer in a hash map to monitor future access to this memory region. It is instrumented after every buffer access to ensure that the buffer's address is correctly captured and monitored.

The instrumented LLVM IR of the example in Listing 1 after the use of BUFFERMONITOR is shown in Listing 3.

```

4  %9 = load i32, i32* %2, align 4
5  %10 = sext i32 %9 to i64
6  %11 = mul i64 %10, 1
7  %12 = bitcast [10 x i8]* %3 to i8*
8  call void @update_buffer(i64 5, i8* %12, i64
   %11)
9  %13 = getelementptr inbounds [10 x i8], [10
   x i8]* %3, i64 0, i64 %10
10 call void @store_buffer_pointer(i32 28, i8*
   %12, i8* %13, i64 %11)
11  ...

```

Listing 3: LLVM IR for memory access with highlighted BUFFERMONITOR instrumentation

The accesses made by the *memcpy* or similar functions are handled accordingly. The function is called for both the destination buffer and the source buffer. In addition, the address calculated by the *getelementptr* instruction can also be accessed, as it is a pointer to the buffer. To detect such accesses, the address is also stored in the hash map by calling the *store_buffer_pointer* function.

4. INTEGRATION OF BUFFERMONITOR IN THE FUZZING WORKFLOW

The integration of BUFFERMONITOR with fuzzing tools is designed to be flexible and adaptable. The instrumented SUT ensures that the gathered information about memory allocations and accesses is stored and subsequently written

to a shared memory that is accessible by a fuzzer. This allows the fuzzer to use the data during the fuzzing process. This methodology allows for the seamless integration of monitoring capabilities into the fuzzing process without requiring significant modifications to the fuzzer.

The fuzzing workflow illustrated in Figure 2 is based on the workflow used in AFL. Nevertheless, this workflow only provides an illustrative overview of the integration of BUFFERMONITOR. The principles and techniques outlined can be adapted and applied to other fuzzing frameworks. By leveraging BUFFERMONITOR within the context of a well-established fuzzing tool, we illustrate how the presented buffer monitoring approach can enhance the detection of buffer overflow vulnerabilities across various testing environments.

Figure 2: Overview of the fuzzing workflow.

Initial seed pool

The fuzzing campaign initially starts with a set of test cases forming the initial seed pool. After selecting a seed from the pool, a score is calculated which provides a measure of the mutation frequency.

Mutation phase

During the mutation phase, new seeds are generated through various operations such as bit flips or arithmetic operations (mutate selected seed).

Seed execution

The mutated seed is then used to execute the instrumented SUT, which contains the BUFFERMONITOR instrumentation. Once the SUT is executed with a mutated seed, the fuzzer processes the runtime information. Here, the data accumulated by the buffer monitor pass is read and processed by the fuzzer. The unique identifier guarantees precise monitoring and documentation of each buffer discovered throughout the fuzzing process, including all accesses.

Storing seeds

After execution, a decision is made on whether to store the mutated seed or not based on the runtime behavior of the SUT. If the SUT exhibits 'interesting' behavior, the seed is saved and added to the seed pool for further test case generation. As the focus is on uncovering buffer overflow vulnerabilities, As the focus is on uncovering buffer overflow vulnerabilities, we favor seeds that have a higher potential seeds will be favored that have a higher potential to trigger them. For this purpose, a seed is stored and added to the seed pool if it causes a new minimal distance. Furthermore, seeds that uncover a new program path will be stored to enhance code coverage.

Weighting Buffer Accesses

To assign higher weights to particularly interesting buffer accesses, a weighting mechanism is employed. Buffer accesses are weighted based on their significance:

- 0: UNFAVORABLE: The buffer was accessed only once.
- 1: NEUTRAL: The distance value from the buffer access decreased once.
- 2: FAVORABLE: The distance value from the buffer access decreased twice.
- 3: VERY_FAVORABLE: The distance value from the buffer access decreased three or more times.

The weighting process facilitates the identification of buffer accesses that are influenced by the SUT's input, thereby distinguishing them from constant, input-independent accesses.

Scoring Function

The scoring function determines how long a seed remains in the mutation phase. Seeds are scored based on their associated memory accesses, with higher weights assigned to more significant accesses (smaller distance). The computed value is multiplied by the aforementioned weighting factors (e.g., a factor of 2 for FAVORABLE) to emphasize its significance. By applying these multipliers, the fuzzer can prioritize seeds that trigger more critical memory access.

Selection Process

In each fuzzing cycle, a seed is selected from the seed pool. Seeds that have never been selected and have caused a minimal distance are prioritized. If no such seed exists, a seed that uncovers a new program path is chosen instead. A seed that has already been selected will not be chosen again unless all other seeds have been selected, ensuring newly added seeds are prioritized.

5. EVALUATION

To assess the effectiveness of integrating BUFFERMONITOR into the fuzzing process, we conducted experiments using MJS [16], a C-based JavaScript interpreter designed to run on microcontrollers. Given that the current implementation of the fuzzer is derived from AFL, AFL is also used as the baseline for evaluating the modified fuzzer. Henceforward, we use AFL* to denote the modified fuzzer incorporating the buffer data in its fuzzing strategy as described in section 4.

We conducted 15 test runs of AFL* in an isolated test environment, with each run lasting 24 hours. To facilitate direct comparisons, we also run AFL under identical conditions and for the same duration. To detect buffer overflows, MJS was compiled with ASan enabling AFL to detect buffer overflows. To establish ground-truth, we inserted 10 buffer overflow vulnerabilities into the SUT. For evaluating AFL*, we are using the following metrics:

- 1) The amount of triggered buffer overflows, counting how many of the inserted buffer overflows were found by the fuzzer.
- 2) The performance, quantified in terms of the number of tests executed during the runs.
- 3) The density of the fuzzing campaign

We define density as the ratio of triggered buffer overflows to the total number of executed tests. This metric offers insight into the fuzzer's efficiency in detecting buffer overflows, with a higher value indicating greater effectiveness in identifying these vulnerabilities.

5.1 Results

Figure 3: Comparison of Buffer Overflows Found: AFL vs. AFL*

Figure 4: Average bug Detection Rates: AFL vs. AFL* Over Time

Figure 3 presents the results from the 15 test runs conducted for both AFL and AFL*. The plots show that AFL* demonstrates a significantly higher detection rate compared to AFL.

Figure 4 shows when each bug was discovered by the two fuzzers throughout the testing period. The results demonstrate that while AFL initially is faster at detecting buffer overflows, AFL* surpasses AFL after approximately six hours of runtime.

Across the 15 fuzzing runs, over 24-hour, AFL executed an average of 31,317,486 test runs, while AFL* performed an average of 70,143,470 test runs within the same time frame. The significant difference in fuzzing performance is due to the performance overhead of 73% imposed by the AddressSanitizer [7].

The density values are displayed in Table 3. The fourth column indicates which fuzzer exhibits the higher density value, indicating more efficient bug detection capabilities. The results reveal that AFL demonstrates a consistently higher density value across all temporal points, meaning fewer runs are required to detect a bug.

Zeit	AFL*	AFL	>
1h	2.50902×10^{-7}	5.61961×10^{-7}	AFL
2h	1.25457×10^{-7}	2.80993×10^{-7}	AFL
3h	3.34552×10^{-7}	8.00405×10^{-7}	AFL
4h	3.76371×10^{-7}	1.43051×10^{-6}	AFL
5h	3.87777×10^{-7}	1.16484×10^{-6}	AFL
6h	4.06785×10^{-7}	9.70704×10^{-7}	AFL
...	AFL

Table 3: Average density values at different points of time during fuzzing for AFL and AFL*.

5.2 Interpretation of Results

The presented results indicate that AFL* is more capable of detecting a larger amount of buffer overflows in the SUT. This seems mostly due to a faster execution speed of the SUT caused by a more lightweight instrumentation, since AFL exhibits a better density value, indicating it finds the bugs more efficiently. AFL appears to struggle with detecting some of the more challenging buffer overflows, indicating the effectiveness of the distance metric introduced by BUFFERMONITOR. AFL* successfully detects the majority of buffer overflows within the initial hours of the fuzzing campaign. In contrast, AFL fails to identify some buffer overflows throughout the entire fuzzing process, as presented in Figure 3. In extreme cases, AFL is only able to detect 6 out of 10 buffer overflows.

6. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we presented BUFFERMONITOR a framework for instrumenting SUTs during compilation to facilitate the monitoring of buffer accesses. Our approach aims to enhance the detection of buffer overflows by integrating BUFFERMONITOR within the fuzzing workflow. By integrating it into a widely used fuzzer, we were able to show that buffer overflows are more likely to be discovered more quickly if the buffer accesses are taken into account. Looking ahead, further evaluations will be performed in diverse and complex software environments.

Additionally, we plan to extend our methodology to detect buffer underflows, which occur when accesses are made to memory locations before the start of a buffer. This extension

will involve similar principles of monitoring memory accesses and calculating distances to the lower boundaries of buffers. By addressing buffer overflows and underflows, our future work aims to provide a more holistic approach to memory safety. We believe that these advancements will contribute significantly to the field of software security and inspire further research and development in this area.

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